

Training Manual 7

Gender in Aquaculture Production Systems

Why Gender Matters in Aquaculture Production Systems

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Module 1: Why Gender Matters in Aquaculture Production Systems

Introduction

Aquaculture is vital for global food security and economic development, with women and men playing significant roles in aquaculture production. Though this true, there is differential constraints that face women and men small-holder farmers in aquaculture systems and these may have far-reaching effects on the productivity of the industry. Gender-responsive approaches therefore matter in aquaculture to promote inclusive innovations, practice, and strategies that contribute to the sustainable sectoral growth. The training manual aims to recognize and integrate gender considerations in aquaculture research, policy, and practice as a strategy to building more inclusive and sustainable aquaculture innovation. Students will gain a comprehensive understanding of gender dynamics in aquaculture production systems. The manual will introduce fundamental gender-related terminologies and clarify the distinctions between gender and sex, highlighting their implications in agricultural and aquaculture contexts. The course will also explore gender roles and how they manifest in aquaculture, emphasizing the division of labor, decision-making, and access to resources. Additionally, it will examine the general constraints faced by women farmers in aquaculture, such as limited access to credit, technology, and market opportunities. By addressing these aspects, the students with the knowledge and skills to analyze and advocate for gender equity in aquaculture and broader agricultural systems.

Module Objectives

At the end of this module, the men and women participants will,

- Gain an understanding of the basic gender related terminologies
- Appreciate the gender roles and how this manifest in aquaculture production system
- Understand the relevant strategies for gender transformation in aquaculture production systems

Module Timing, Location, and Materials required

No	Session	Estimated time	Location
1.	What is gender?	2 hrs	Aquaculture Community
2.	Gender roles and how they manifest in aquaculture production systems	2 hrs	
3.	Gender transformative strategies in in Aquaculture	1.5 hrs	
4.	Training Materials: Flip charts, flash cards, pictures of men and women, masking tape, assorted markers		

Session 1: Definition of Gender and other Basic Related Terminologies

Interactive Activity 1. Individual Reflection:

The word gender has been used several times and am very sure you have heard about these terms. As an individual, reflection your understanding of the word gender. Take a few minutes and reflect on what you think is the definition of this terms. Write down your thoughts on the flash cards provide and one thought per flash card. The facilitators take the cards and clusters them according to the different responses of the learners.

Facilitator's Notes

What is Gender?

Gender is a complex and multifaceted concept that refers to the social, cultural, and psychological attributes and roles that societies assign to individuals based on perceived sex differences. This means that gender is not simply biological but is shaped by cultural, social, and historical contexts. It encompasses the expectations, norms, and responsibilities that society attributes to individuals based on whether they are perceived as male or female. Understanding gender therefore involves recognizing the distinction between sex (the biological attributes) and gender (the social and cultural roles and identities). Many times, gender and sex are used interchangeably. In this session, I will go a step ahead and differentiate between gender and sex

Table 1: Distinctions between Gender and Sex

Sex (male/female)	Gender (men/women)
Biologically defined and genetically acquired differences between males and females	Socially defined and culturally learned differences between men and women (masculinity femininity)
Biological characteristics	Socially constructed/expected set of roles, responsibilities, behaviours associated with being a girl and boy or women and men
Defines males and females independently of each other	Defines men and women with reference to the socio-cultural power relations between them (entitlements, positions)
The definition is universal	Definitions of men and women vary from place to place/ overtime/ context

Let me also share with you various illustrations on how different schools of thought differentiate between sex and gender (see figure 1)

Figure 1: Differences between Sex and Gender

These definitions imply that gender is not something that is biologically acquired but rather, assigned by a given society. It sets expectations on how one conducts him/herself and therefore sets the rules for behavior in a particular context. This also means the interpretation and application of gender identity are deeply rooted in the norms and values of a given society and thus vary from one context to the other. So, gender encompasses the roles, behaviors, activities, and expectations that society considers appropriate for men and women. Sex on the other hand refers to the biological and physical attributes that differentiate males and females. Understanding the distinction between gender and sex is essential for appreciating the diverse ways individuals express their identities and navigate their social environments. Because gender is a complex and multifaceted concept, it has led to the emergence of numerous terms that capture the diversity of human experiences and identities. I will now discuss other gender-related terms that will be important when discussing the roles that many and women play in the aquaculture industry.

Social norms are the often implicit, informal rules that most people accept and abide by. They are influenced by belief systems, perceptions of what others expect and do, and sometimes by perceived rewards and sanctions. Norms are embedded in formal and informal institutions and produced and reproduced through social interaction.

Gender norms are expected behaviors of men (masculinity) and women (femininity), and often age, in a given social context. The internalization of all these norms and values is occurs through socialization. They often reflect and cement inequitable gender relations. For instance, in some Ugandan cultures, there are gender norms that women should do not go to the lake to fish.

Gender discrimination: Preferential or restrictive treatment where one sex is disadvantaged because the other is favored. It can result from individual behavior, or it can be systemic. Systemic gender discrimination describes behavior, policies or practices that are part of the structures or culture of a social institution.

Gender equality means that there is no discrimination on the grounds of a person's sex in the allocation of resources or benefits or in their access to services. For instance, using the exact same measure or quantity; and/or affecting all objects in the same way.

Gender equality refers to the ability of men and women to have equal opportunities and life chances.

Let me discuss the term gender equality and gender equity in some details so that you can understand the difference between the two for I will be using these a little more than the other definitions

Interactive Activity 2: Peer to Peer Session

1. Pair up with the person of your choice. Read the scenario provide and answer the questions that follow.

In a small village in Uganda, a new aquaculture program has been introduced to support local fish farmers to enhance their investment in fish farming. Free training, fish fingerlings, and feeds have been providing to support the farmers. To receive the support however, farmers must travel to the sub-county office, fill out written forms for commitment to the project, and show proof of land ownership. James, a male highly educated farmer, own fish pond and a car. Jane is an illiterate woman farmer who uses her husband's land for fish farming, but her name is not on the land documents. She is 22 years old and mother of four young children to take care daily. Joan is a 28-year-old woman with a physical disability and owns a fish pond on family owned land.

- In this aquaculture enterprise, what challenges did Jane and Joan face that James did not?
- What changes can be made in fish farming programs to ensure that women and persons with disabilities can fully benefit and participate?
- Why is it important to provide different kinds of support to different farmers in aquaculture instead of giving everyone the same thing?

Ask some pairs to share the answers in a plenary session

Session 2: Gender Roles in Aquaculture Production Systems

Interactive Activity 2. Group Exercise

1. Divide the class into small groups and assign each group one role card of a given stakeholder in the aquaculture industry. Encourage them to discuss their assigned role and imagine a day in the life of their character. They should think about:
 - How gender influences their character's work: What tasks do they do? How are they perceived by others?
 - Gender-specific challenges or advantages: Are there any barriers the character faces or benefits because of their sex?
 - Decision-making and interactions: How do gender roles affect their interactions with colleagues or superiors?

Reflection

1. *What challenges did the characters face because of their gender?*
2. *How can these challenges be addressed in the aquaculture industry?*
3. *Are there any opportunities for women and men in aquaculture that are unique to their gender roles?*
4. *What are some ways to promote gender equality and equity within the industry?*

Facilitator's Notes

Gender roles refer to the socially expected behaviors and responsibilities assigned to men and women based on social expectations and contextual factors

Figure 3: General Gender Roles in Society

Traditional gender norms dictate how women and men “should” behave in society expecting women to be polite and demure, and men to suppress emotions. The overall message however is that everyone, regardless of gender, should have the freedom to express themselves as individual

“This image helps us question the rigid gender expectations placed on both women and men. It invites us to reflect on how these stereotypes limit personal freedom and emotional well-being.

Table 2: Broad Typologies of Gender Roles in the Aquaculture Industry

Gender Role	Description
Productive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Refers to work done by both women and men in exchange for payment</i> • <i>Typically involves activities in the formal labor market or other income-generating endeavors</i> • <i>Varied occupations and professions fall under this category</i> • <i>Recognized as contributing to the economic output and development of society</i>
Reproductive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Involves child rearing responsibilities and domestic tasks</i> • <i>Ensures the maintenance and well-being of all family members</i> • <i>Primarily performed by individuals within the family unit</i> • <i>Often unpaid or undervalued in terms of monetary compensation</i>
Community Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Primarily focuses on the management and provision of resources</i> • <i>Aims to ensure the functioning and well-being of the community as a whole</i> • <i>Includes activities such as organizing public services, infrastructure development, and resource allocation</i> • <i>Essential for the sustainability and growth of the community</i>

The aquaculture value chain involves several stages—from input supply to production, collection, processing, trading, and finally consumption. At each stage, different actors play important roles, and gender division of labour can be clearly observed. Men are often dominant in the early stages of the chain, especially in input supply and fish production. They typically own or manage fish ponds, handle large-scale operations, and have better access to resources such as land, capital, and technical training. Women, on the other hand, are more commonly found in the lower-value or supportive roles, such as feeding fish, cleaning ponds, and handling post-harvest activities like fish sorting, drying, and selling in local markets. In collection and processing, women may be involved in tasks such as cleaning, gutting, packaging, and drying fish, especially when processing is done by hand or in small-scale settings. However, men often dominate the more commercial or mechanized processing activities.

Source: *Modification from WORLD FISH*

When it comes to trading, women tend to operate as retailers in local markets, while men are more involved in large-scale wholesale and export businesses. These gendered roles reflect differences in access to decision-making power, resources, and market opportunities. Support institutions like agriculture departments, NGOs, and banks often design programs without fully addressing these gender roles, which can lead to unequal benefits. Therefore, understanding and addressing the gender division of labour is essential to ensure that both women and men can participate meaningfully and benefit fairly from opportunities within the aquaculture value chain.

WorldFish highlights the critical yet often overlooked role of **gender and women in fisheries and aquaculture**. It emphasizes that while aquaculture is a growing global industry with great potential for economic development and food security, **women remain underrepresented especially in decision-making, technical, and leadership roles**. Gender-related challenges, such as limited access to resources, technology, healthcare, and training, hinder women's full participation so **gender-responsive policies, inclusive innovation, and empowering women is essential for sustainable and resilient aquatic food systems**.

Session 3 : Gender transformative strategies for women in fisheries and aquaculture systems

Activity 3: Individual Reflection

Take a few quiet moments to respond to the questions below. Be honest and consider your own role in promoting positive change.

- *What comes to your mind when you hear the concept of gender transformation mean in the aquaculture production system?*
- *In my current work as a fish farmer, are there practices that reinforce traditional gender roles?*
- *What behaviour or initiatives can be implemented to empower women fishers or challenge unequal power relations in aquaculture production systems?*

Share of your answers in a plenary

Facilitator's Notes

Women in aquaculture face significant constraints, including limited access to land, credit, training, and modern technologies. Cultural norms often confine them to unpaid domestic roles, restricting their time, mobility, and participation in decision-making. These barriers prevent women from fully benefiting from or contributing to aquaculture value chains, despite their involvement in key activities such as fish feeding, processing, and marketing. Transforming the aquaculture sector to address these gendered challenges is critical for improving productivity, equity, and sustainability. The Global Programme Sustainable Fisheries and Aquaculture, Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) provide some key activities to empower women in aquaculture production systems (see figure 4)

Figure 4. Decision making for men and women

Key activities to empower women in fisheries and aquaculture include conducting gender-focused value chain analysis, offering tailored capacity-building programs, and raising public awareness on gender issues. These approaches help identify existing inequalities, equip women with relevant skills, and create a more inclusive environment for participation across all levels of the aquaculture sector. Further efforts involve encouraging shared ownership and knowledge exchange among women, supporting their leadership within communities, and strengthening platforms for engagement at local, regional, and national levels. These integrated strategies enhance women's decision-making power, access to resources, and visibility, fostering sustainable and gender-equitable growth in fisheries and aquaculture.

Summary

The training manual underscores the importance of integrating gender perspectives into aquaculture systems to foster inclusive and sustainable aquaculture production systems. It highlights the distinct roles and constraints experienced by men and women in aquaculture, emphasizing the need for gender-responsive strategies. By clarifying key gender concepts and exploring how social norms and gender roles shape participation in aquaculture value chains, women and men farmers can analyze and challenge key gender inequalities in the aquaculture production systems. Gender-transformative approach through tailored training, inclusive policies, and structural change can help dismantle barriers, enhance women's participation and leadership, and ultimately boost the resilience and productivity of the aquaculture sector. Promoting equity, not just equality, is key to ensuring that all actors regardless of gender benefit fairly from aquaculture innovations and opportunities.

Module Key Messages

- Smallholder women fishers in Uganda often face limited access to land, credit, and training, which restricts their ability to own ponds or invest in quality inputs. Aquaculture programs must adapt their support systems to recognize user rights on family land as to ensure that women can participate equitably.
- In many smallholder settings, men are seen as the primary fish producers while women handle tasks like feeding and marketing, often without decision-making power. Challenging these traditional roles through community dialogues and inclusive group formation can help shift attitudes and promote shared responsibilities in aquaculture households.
- Gender-transformative approaches that involve women in savings groups, technical and leadership can empower smallholder women fishers and consequently enhance their confidence, access resources, and contribute more meaningfully to the growth of their aquaculture enterprises.

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